

Energizing Education: Examining the Financial Analysis of The University of Abuja Solar Mini Grid Project Using the FINPLAN Methodology

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Executive Summary

This study assesses the financial feasibility of the proposed University of Abuja solar hybrid mini-grid employing the Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN), with particular emphasis on tariff and exchange rate risks. The findings demonstrate that the project is financially sustainable under the 70:30 debt–equity structure, yielding a substantial positive net present value of ₦19-20 billion, and an internal rate of return of 24-25%, exceeding standard infrastructure benchmarks at the baseline tariff of ₦68.35 per kWh. Sensitivity analysis reveals that tariffs are the most critical factor for project sustainability, with a break-even point of approximately ₦38 per kWh. Exchange rate depreciation reduces project value (i.e., as it weakens from ₦1,480/USD to ₦2,380/USD, the NPV declines steadily (₦20 billion to below ₦2 billion).

The study recommends maintaining tariffs that are both cost-reflective and predictable, expanding concessional and local-currency financing to reduce foreign exchange risk, and increasing the use of solar hybrid mini-grids through the Energizing Education Programme. Additional suggestions include promoting local assembly of renewable energy components and enhancing financial risk management to improve project bankability and sustainability. These approaches aim to reduce diesel dependence, lower operational costs, and support Nigeria’s energy transition objectives.

1.0 Introduction

Nigeria has one of the lowest grid-based electricity capacities worldwide, with a population of over [232 million \(World Bank, 2024\)](#), and an installed capacity of 13,000 MW, but only 8,500 MW of transmission capacity. The daily dispatch is approximately 4,500 MW due to limitations in gas supply and transmission. The estimated demand is about 20,000 MW, with much of it supplied by off-grid diesel generators.¹

As education is crucial for national development, boosting skills, workforce competence, reducing income inequality, and fostering innovation, a key challenge in Nigeria's education system is unreliable electricity at research and higher institutions, caused by limited access and inadequate power. This makes learning environments inhospitable for educators and students.

The Nigerian government, via [the Nigeria Electrification Project \(NEP\)](#) with support from AfDB and the World Bank, launched the [Energizing Education Programme \(EEP\)](#), executed by the [Rural Electrification Agency \(REA\)](#). Its aim is to provide reliable, sustainable electricity to Federal Universities and hospitals through solar hybrid plants and infrastructure upgrades. Three phases have been completed.

With [a student population of over 20,000](#) and a total population of over 40,000, the University of Abuja is located at the heart of Nigeria's federal capital, making it a centre of learning and research. Under the EEP, the university is being considered for inclusion in phase IV.

In light of the above, this project aims to deliver a clean, reliable, and cost-effective solar mini-grid to a federal university by analysing the financial feasibility and sustainability of the University of Abuja solar mini-grid using the Model for Financial Analysis of Electric Sector Expansion Plans (FINPLAN). It will focus on how different financing structures and economic assumptions influence project viability throughout its lifecycle. The objectives include: (a) evaluating the financial viability of the project under various debt–equity structures and tariff frameworks, and (b) assessing how key financial risks, particularly electricity price and exchange rate fluctuations, affect project bankability and returns through the NPV and IRR values.

¹ <https://www.savannah-energy.com/operations/hydrocarbons/nigeria/market-opportunity/>

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Modeling Approach/Tool Implemented

The University of Abuja Solar Mini Grid Project will use the FINPLAN modelling approach, developed by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), for planning and decision-making in energy projects.

2.2 Data sources

The data is collected from sources such as the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, the Central Bank of Nigeria, the Nigeria Tax Act, and the Federal Reserve of the US.

Table 1: Technical, Financial, and Economic Data/Assumption for the Case Study

TECHNICAL DATA/ ASSUMPTIONS	FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC DATA/ ASSUMPTIONS	FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC DATA/ ASSUMPTIONS
Type: Solar PV mini-grid with battery storage	Currency: USD (Foreign) and Naira (Domestic)	Unit cost of electricity (Tariff): ₦68.35 or 4.62 cents
Capacity: 10.00 MW	Inflation Rate: (\$) 2.7%; (₦) 13%	Tax: VAT (7.5%) at 10% of the investment; CIT (25%); WHT (10%)
Construction Period: 2 years (2026-2027)	Exchange Rate: ₦1,480: \$1	Depreciation: Linear (2%) at 15 years
Life span: 25 years (2026-2051)	Stakeholders: African Development Bank (AfDB), World Bank, and the Nigerian Government (NGN) through the private sector	Finance: Debt (70%-\$12 million); Debt Duration: 15 years; Equity (30%- \$4 million/₦ 5,920 million)
Projected Annual Generation: 43.8 GWh	Project Cost: \$16 million	Annual O&M Cost: ₦ 96 million
	Spread Above Inflation: 1.5% Inflation: 13% (Steady Rate)	Financing Ratios: NPV, IRR

2.3 Assumptions

Table 2: Assumption Table of the Case Study

Parameter	Value
Discount Rate	14%
Disposal Year	2051
Depreciation	Linear (15%0
Decommissioning	External Trust
Plant (Study Type), Product, Ownership	Single Plant, Electricity, Utility
Percentage of Investment	10%

2.4 Sensitivity analysis

The two simulation scenarios (electricity price/tariff and exchange rate) are considered as described in Table 02. The analysis will consider parameters such as the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and the Net Present Value (NPV). These scenarios were selected as they have macroeconomic implications for the project. For example, the electricity tariff simulation helps us assess the minimum break-even price, the project's bankability, and its sustainability. As 70% of the project comes via the USD, investors' confidence was modelled by exchange-rate movements.

3.0 Results

3.1 Sensitivity Analysis 1: Electricity price variation with a focus on IRR, NPV, and Dividend Payment

The base value of the price of electricity is **₦68.35/kWh**, which corresponds to the [Band parameter](#) of Nigeria (i.e., Band B- the tariff paid by the middle class). This first scenario analyses the impact of variations in electricity prices on the project's profitability, varying the price from **₦68.35/kWh** to **₦25.35/kWh**. The 10 levels of electricity prices are used to evaluate their impact on NPV and IRR.

Figure 01 shows that for electricity prices above **₦38.35/kWh**, the NPV and the IRR remain above 14.0%. Although at **₦28.35/kWh**, the IRR becomes zero.

Figure 1: Electricity Price (Tariff) Sensitivity Analysis

The project is highly sensitive to electricity tariff levels. As tariffs escalate, both Net Present Value (NPV) and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) consistently improve, indicating enhanced project bankability. The project breaks even at approximately **₦38:35** per kilowatt-hour (kWh), at which the NPV becomes positive and the IRR is approximately 14–15%, representing the minimum tariff required for financial viability.

At the baseline tariff of **₦68.35/kWh**, the project demonstrates robust performance, generating an estimated NPV of **₦19–20 billion** and an IRR of approximately 24–25%, which considerably exceeds typical hurdle rates for infrastructure projects.

Tariffs below the breakeven threshold result in negative NPVs (i.e., at **₦33.35**, the NPV becomes negative **₦3.376.86 billion** with an IRR of 10.51, at **₦28.35**, the NPV becomes negative **₦7.854.18 billion** with an IRR of zero while at **₦23.35**, the NPV becomes negative **₦13.534.12 billion** with an IRR of zero), and sharply declining IRRs, rendering

the project financially unviable at tariffs between ₦28/kWh–₦33/kWh, where the IRR approaches zero.

The analysis affirms that tariffs that accurately reflect costs and align with NEP and EEP principles are crucial to ensuring long-term financial sustainability while maintaining the university's provision of reliable and affordable power.

3.1.1 Base Price: ₦68.35/kWh

Figure 2: Dividend Payment at Base Price (₦68.35/kWh)

Figure 2 shows that a shareholder will receive a dividend after 8 years. The dividend payment will start in 2034 and continue for 17 years, until 2051.

3.1.2 Break-Even Price: ₦38.35/kWh

Figure 3: Dividend Payment at Base Price (₦38.35/kWh)

Figure 3 shows that a shareholder will receive a dividend after 18 years. The dividend payment will start in 2044 and continue for 7 years, until 2051, showing a longer waiting time.

3.2 Sensitivity Analysis 2: Exchange Rate Variation

Figure 4: Exchange Rate Sensitivity Analysis

Figure 4 shows that the project's financial performance is moderately sensitive to Naira depreciation. As the exchange rate weakens from **₦1,480/USD to ₦2,380/USD**, the project's **NPV declines steadily** from about **₦20 billion to below ₦2 billion**, reflecting the higher naira cost of dollar-denominated capital expenditures, debt service, and imported components. The **IRR falls gradually** from approximately **24.5% to about 19%**, indicating reduced but still positive investment attractiveness under severe depreciation scenarios. Across the board, the project remains **financially viable**, with IRR staying well above typical concessionary and commercial hurdle rates, **suggesting strong resilience**. The analysis highlights foreign exchange risk as a key driver of value erosion (loss of economic value), underscoring the importance of concessional FX-linked financing, local-currency revenue indexation, and partial local-content sourcing to preserve project bankability amid Nigeria's volatile macroeconomic conditions.

5.0 Discussion

Results from this case study indicate a viable, bankable project. It shows the importance of variables such as IRR and NPV in energy project investment. The analysis reveals that under the 70:30 debt-equity structure, and at the base price of ₦68.35, there is a strong **positive NPV of ₦19–20 billion (\$12.84-13.51 million) and an IRR of 24-25%. This represents a 52.6316% increase in the IRR and a 193.354% increase in the NPV relative to the breakeven tariff.**

The findings of the financial analysis demonstrate that solar photovoltaic (PV) hybrid mini-grids with integrated battery storage represent a technically and financially viable solution for improving electricity provision within Nigerian tertiary institutions. The model shows that the success of these projects largely depends on maintaining cost-reflective tariffs and effectively managing major financial risks, especially those related to electricity prices and exchange rate volatility. These findings align with the main goals of the Nigeria Electrification Project and the Energizing Education Programme, which focus on delivering reliable, affordable, and sustainable electricity to public institutions while decreasing dependence on diesel generation.'

The study highlights key policy areas needing government action. It emphasizes the importance of maintaining transparent and predictable tariff structures that enable cost recovery and ensure affordability. When tariffs fail to cover operational costs, targeted support measures such as viability gap funding or concessional loans may be necessary.

While these measures involve costs, they are likely less burdensome than the long-term economic and environmental impacts of diesel generation. Expanding access to concessional financing, guarantees, and local-currency loans can lower exchange-rate risks and improve project bankability. Policies that promote the local assembly of solar components could reduce foreign exchange risk and strengthen local value chains. The study offers valuable insights but has limitations, including reliance on assumed

parameters that may differ from actual conditions. Its deterministic sensitivity analysis evaluates one variable at a time, limiting understanding of the combined effects of shocks such as inflation, currency depreciation, and tariffs. It also doesn't account for operational uncertainties such as demand changes, equipment issues, battery degradation, or payment delays, nor does it fully model institutional and regulatory risks affecting implementation.

Future research could improve the robustness of the analysis by integrating probabilistic modeling to better handle macroeconomic and operational uncertainties. Enhancing data collection on load profiles, energy demand, and long-term costs would make financial projections more accurate. Exploring alternative financing options, such as blended finance and results-based funding, can help identify cost-effective ways to expand renewable energy in public institutions. Additionally, future studies should address implementation challenges such as procurement delays, foreign exchange risks, and institutional capacity constraints, as these are crucial for the long-term success and scale-up of mini-grid projects in Nigeria.

6.0 Conclusion

This study assessed the financial viability of the proposed University of Abuja solar mini-grid using the FINPLAN methodology and examined the effects of key financial risks, particularly electricity tariffs and exchange-rate movements. The analysis demonstrates that tariff levels are the most significant determinant of project sustainability, while exchange-rate depreciation reduces project value but does not necessarily undermine viability within the tested range. These findings highlight the importance of sound tariff design, concessional financing, and foreign exchange risk management in renewable energy projects in Nigeria.

The key lesson from this study is that the government should prioritize transparent, predictable, and cost-reflective tariff frameworks for public-sector renewable energy projects. It should also expand access to **concessional and local-currency financing**, including partial credit guarantees and FX-hedging instruments, to reduce exposure to exchange-rate volatility.

Distributed renewable energy systems can provide reliable, sustainable electricity to public institutions when supported by appropriate financial and policy frameworks. It is recommended that the government continue expanding solar mini-grid deployment under the Energizing Education Programme, strengthen access to concessional and local-currency financing, and promote policies that encourage local content and cost efficiency. These measures would improve project bankability, reduce diesel dependence, and support Nigeria's broader energy transition objectives.

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